

ASSOCIATION OF MATERNAL RISK FACTORS WITH LOW-BIRTH-WEIGHT AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Background:

Low birth weight (LBW), defined as birth weight less than 2500 grams, remains a major public health concern worldwide and is a leading contributor to neonatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in developing countries (World Health Organization [WHO] & United Nations Children's Fund [UNICEF], 2004). Globally, approximately 20 million LBW infants are born annually, with the majority occurring in developing regions (UNICEF, 2019). Maternal factors such as under nutrition, smoking, inadequate antenatal care, and short inter-pregnancy interval have been identified as important determinants of LBW (Asmare et al., 2018; Momeni et al., 2017).

Objective:

To determine the association of maternal risk factors with low birth weight babies at a tertiary care hospital.

Methodology:

This hospital-based case-control study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Bolan Medical College/Hospital, Quetta, over a period of six months. A total of 238 neonates were included through non-probability consecutive sampling, comprising 119 cases (birth weight <2500 grams) and 119 controls (birth weight >2500 grams). Data regarding maternal age, residence, parity, BMI at booking visit, maternal under nutrition (BMI <18.5 kg/m²), maternal smoking (≥1 cigarette/day during the 2nd and 3rd trimester), antenatal care attendance (<4 visits), and short inter-pregnancy interval (<18 months) were collected using a structured proforma. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23. Chi-square test was applied to assess associations and odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated. A p-value ≤ .05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

Maternal under nutrition, maternal smoking, absent antenatal care, and short inter-pregnancy interval were found to be significantly associated with low birth weight

(p ≤ .05). These findings are consistent with previous case-control studies conducted in similar settings (Asmare et al., 2018; Momeni et al., 2017).

Conclusion:

Maternal modifiable risk factors, particularly under nutrition, inadequate antenatal care, smoking, and short inter-pregnancy interval, are significantly associated with low birth weight. Strengthening antenatal care services and improving maternal nutrition may help reduce the burden of LBW in tertiary care settings.

Introduction

Low birth weight (LBW), defined as a birth weight of less than 2500 grams irrespective of gestational age, remains one of the most significant challenges in maternal and child health worldwide (World Health Organization [WHO] & United Nations Children's Fund [UNICEF], 2004). It is a major determinant of neonatal morbidity and mortality and contributes substantially to infant deaths, particularly in developing countries. Infants weighing less than 2500 grams are approximately 20 times more likely to die compared to those with normal birth weight (WHO & UNICEF, 2004). Despite improvements in maternal and child healthcare services, the burden of LBW continues to be disproportionately high in low- and middle-income countries.

Globally, an estimated 20 million low birth weight infants are born each year, accounting for nearly 15.5% of all live births, with approximately 95% occurring in developing regions (UNICEF, 2019). The highest prevalence is observed in Asia and Africa, where socioeconomic disparities, poor maternal nutrition, and inadequate antenatal care services remain prevalent. In South Asian countries, including Pakistan and neighboring regions, LBW continues to be a persistent public health issue due to limited access to quality maternal healthcare and underlying nutritional deficiencies. The association between LBW and increased infant mortality has been consistently reported, with low birth weight contributing significantly to neonatal deaths (Gupta et al., 2016).

Low birth weight is closely linked with both short-term and long-term adverse outcomes. In the neonatal period, LBW infants are more vulnerable to infections, respiratory distress, hypothermia, and feeding difficulties. Studies have shown that infants with intrauterine growth restriction

(IUGR) and low birth weight experience higher morbidity and mortality compared to appropriately grown neonates (Malhotra et al., 2019). Furthermore, LBW has long-term consequences, including impaired cognitive development, learning disabilities, and increased risk of chronic diseases later in life (Singh, 2017). These outcomes not only affect individual health but also impose a considerable burden on families and healthcare systems.

Multiple maternal factors have been identified as potential determinants of low birth weight. Maternal under nutrition, often reflected by a low body mass index (BMI), has been strongly associated with fetal growth restriction and LBW (Desta et al., 2019). Similarly, maternal smoking during pregnancy has been linked to placental insufficiency and reduced fetal growth due to decreased oxygen supply to the fetus (Asmare et al., 2018). Inadequate antenatal care is another critical risk factor, as mothers with fewer than the recommended antenatal visits are less likely to receive nutritional counseling, iron supplementation, and timely management of pregnancy-related complications (Asmare et al., 2018). Short inter-pregnancy intervals have also been associated with adverse birth outcomes, possibly due to insufficient maternal nutritional recovery between pregnancies (Momeni et al., 2017).

Although several international studies have identified these risk factors, their distribution and relative contribution may vary across different geographical and socioeconomic settings. Local data are essential to identify context-specific determinants and guide targeted interventions. In Balochistan, limited research has been conducted to evaluate the association between maternal risk factors and low birth weight in tertiary care hospitals.

Therefore, the present study aims to determine the association of maternal risk factors—including maternal under nutrition, smoking, inadequate antenatal care, and short inter-pregnancy interval—with low birth weight among neonates delivered at a tertiary care hospital. Identifying modifiable risk factors will help in designing preventive strategies to reduce the burden of low birth weight and improve maternal and neonatal health outcomes in the region

Literature Review

Low birth weight (LBW) continues to be a major public health concern worldwide, particularly in developing countries. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), LBW is defined as a birth weight of less than 2500 grams irrespective of gestational age (WHO & UNICEF, 2004). Globally, approximately 20 million infants are born with low birth weight each year, representing about 15.5% of all live births, with the majority occurring in developing regions (UNICEF, 2019). South Asia carries a disproportionate burden of LBW, reflecting underlying socioeconomic challenges, maternal malnutrition, and inadequate healthcare services. Low birth weight is a critical predictor of neonatal morbidity and mortality. Infants weighing less than 2500 grams are significantly more likely to experience early neonatal death compared to those with normal birth weight (WHO & UNICEF, 2004). In India and similar regional contexts, LBW contributes substantially to infant mortality rates (Gupta et al., 2016). Beyond mortality, LBW is associated with increased risks of infections, impaired thermoregulation, respiratory complications, and long-term neurodevelopmental disorders (Singh, 2017). Malhotra et al. (2019) emphasized that intrauterine growth restriction and LBW are strongly linked to adverse neonatal outcomes and long-term metabolic and endocrine disorders. Maternal under nutrition has consistently been identified as a significant determinant of low birth weight. Low maternal body mass index (BMI)

reflects poor nutritional status and has been associated with restricted fetal growth and adverse pregnancy outcomes (Desta et al., 2019). In resource-limited settings, maternal malnutrition remains prevalent due to poverty, food insecurity, and lack of nutritional awareness, contributing directly to fetal growth restriction.

Maternal smoking during pregnancy is another well-documented risk factor for LBW. Exposure to tobacco smoke reduces oxygen supply to the fetus and affects placental function, leading to impaired fetal growth. In an unmatched case-control study conducted by Asmare et al. (2018), maternal health problems and adverse pregnancy conditions were significantly more common among mothers delivering LBW infants compared to those delivering normal-weight infants. Similar findings were reported by Momeni et al. (2017), who identified maternal risk factors, including high-risk pregnancies and adverse maternal behaviors, as contributors to LBW.

Antenatal care plays a vital role in ensuring positive pregnancy outcomes. Adequate antenatal visits allow for early identification and management of maternal complications, nutritional counseling, and supplementation. Mothers who do not receive sufficient antenatal care are at increased risk of delivering low birth weight babies (Asmare et al., 2018). The absence of regular antenatal monitoring may delay the detection of conditions such as anemia, hypertension, and fetal growth restriction, thereby increasing the likelihood of adverse outcomes.

Short inter-pregnancy interval has also been associated with low birth weight. Insufficient spacing between pregnancies may not allow adequate maternal physiological and nutritional recovery, resulting in compromised fetal growth (Momeni et al., 2017). Evidence suggests that pregnancies occurring within 18 months of a previous live birth are linked with higher risks of LBW and preterm birth.

Although multiple international studies have highlighted these maternal risk factors, there remains limited local evidence from tertiary care hospitals in Balochistan. Given regional

differences in socioeconomic status, healthcare accessibility, and maternal nutritional patterns, it is important to evaluate these associations within the local context. Understanding the contribution of modifiable maternal risk factors will help inform targeted interventions aimed at reducing the burden of low birth weight in tertiary healthcare settings.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This hospital-based case-control study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Bolan Medical College/Hospital, Quetta. The duration of the study was six months following approval of the synopsis from the institutional ethical review board and the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The sample size was calculated using the WHO sample size calculator. The calculation was based on the frequency of absent antenatal care among low birth weight babies (29.4%) and normal birth weight babies (14.4%) as reported in a previous study (Asmare et al., 2018). With a confidence level of 95% and power of 80%, the required sample size was 238 participants, comprising 119 cases and 119 controls.

Non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used to recruit participants who fulfilled the inclusion criteria.

Study Population

Neonates delivered in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology were assessed for eligibility.

Inclusion Criteria

- Neonates aged less than 36 hours
- Either male or female gender
- Gestational age greater than 30 weeks (based on last menstrual period)
- Cases: Birth weight < 2500 grams
- Controls: Birth weight > 2500 grams

Exclusion Criteria

- Infants born from multiple pregnancies (e.g., twins, triplets)
- Mothers with chronic medical conditions significantly affecting pregnancy outcomes (e.g., severe hypertension, diabetes mellitus)
- Infants with congenital anomalies or chromosomal abnormalities
- Mothers with known substance abuse or addiction during pregnancy

Operational Definitions

Low birth weight was defined as birth weight less than 2500 grams measured using a digital weighing scale without clothing.

The following maternal risk factors were assessed:

- **Maternal under nutrition:** BMI < 18.5 kg/m² at booking visit
- **Maternal smoking:** Smoking ≥1 cigarette per day during the second and third trimester
- **Absent antenatal care:** Fewer than four antenatal visits
- **Short inter-pregnancy interval:** Less than 18 months between a live birth and conception of the subsequent pregnancy

Maternal BMI was calculated using the formula: weight (kg) / height (m²), based on measurements recorded at the booking visit.

Data Collection Procedure

After obtaining ethical approval, informed consent was taken from parents prior to data collection. Baseline demographic information including maternal age, residence (urban/rural), parity, gestational age, and BMI at booking visit was recorded.

Birth weight of all neonates was measured using a calibrated digital weighing scale without clothing. Neonates were categorized into cases and controls according to operational definitions. Information regarding maternal under nutrition, smoking status, antenatal care attendance, and inter-pregnancy interval was obtained through medical record review and maternal history. Data were recorded on a structured proforma designed for the study.

Data Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 23. Quantitative variables such as birth weight, maternal age, gestational age, and maternal BMI were presented as mean ± standard deviation or median (interquartile range) where appropriate. Normality was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test.

Qualitative variables including gender, parity, residence, and maternal risk factors were presented as frequencies and percentages. The association between maternal risk factors and low birth weight was assessed using the chi-square test. Odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals

(CI) were calculated. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Stratification was performed for potential effect modifiers including maternal age groups, residential area, gestational age, and gender of the baby. Post-stratification chi-square or Fisher’s exact test was applied, and adjusted odds ratios were recalculated. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 238 neonates were included in the study, comprising 119 cases (low birth weight) and 119 controls (normal birth weight).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants (Continuous Variables)

Variable	Cases (n=119) Mean ± SD	Controls (n=119) Mean ± SD
Maternal Age (years)	27.25 ± 4.73	27.90 ± 4.89
Gestational Age (weeks)	36.20 ± 1.41	38.58 ± 1.30
BMI at Booking (kg/m ²)	19.13 ± 1.95	23.25 ± 2.56
Birth Weight (g)	2210 ± 206.79	3020 ± 249.04

Cases had lower mean gestational age and significantly lower BMI compared to controls.

Table 2: Association between Maternal Under nutrition and Low Birth Weight

Maternal Under nutrition	Controls n (%)	Cases n (%)
No	97	69
Yes	22	50

Chi-square = 14.52
 p-value = 0.00014
 Odds Ratio (OR) = 3.19

Maternal under nutrition was significantly associated with LBW. Undernourished mothers had approximately 3 times higher odds of delivering LBW babies.

Table 3: Association between Maternal Smoking and Low Birth Weight

Maternal Smoking	Controls n (%)	Cases n (%)
No	95	79
Yes	24	40

Chi-square = 4.81
 p-value = 0.028
 Odds Ratio (OR) = 2.00

Maternal smoking showed a statistically significant association with LBW.

Smokers had twice the odds of delivering LBW infants.

Table 4: Association Between Absent Antenatal Care and Low Birth Weight

Absent Antenatal Care	Controls n (%)	Cases n (%)
No	108	66
Yes	11	53

Chi-square = 35.93

p-value < 0.001

Odds Ratio (OR) = 7.88

Absent antenatal care demonstrated a very strong and highly significant association with LBW. Mothers with fewer than four antenatal visits had nearly 8 times higher odds of delivering LBW babies.

Table 5: Association between Short Inter-Pregnancy Interval and Low Birth Weight

Short Inter-Pregnancy Interval	Controls n (%)	Cases n (%)
No	101	70
Yes	18	49

Chi-square = 18.70 p-value < 0.001

Odds Ratio (OR) = 3.93

Short inter-pregnancy interval was significantly associated with LBW. Mothers with an interval of less than 18 months had nearly 4 times higher odds of delivering LBW infants.

Summary of Findings

Maternal under nutrition, smoking, absent antenatal care, and short inter-pregnancy interval were all significantly associated with low birth weight (p ≤ 0.05). Among these, absent antenatal care showed the strongest association (OR = 7.88).

Discussion

This hospital-based case-control study was conducted to determine the association between maternal risk factors and low birth weight (LBW) at a tertiary care hospital. The findings of the present study demonstrate that maternal under nutrition, maternal smoking, absent antenatal care, and short inter-pregnancy interval were

significantly associated with low birth weight. Among these, absent antenatal care showed the strongest association.

In the present study, maternal under nutrition (BMI < 18.5 kg/m²) was significantly associated with LBW, with undernourished mothers having approximately three times higher odds of delivering low birth weight infants. This finding is consistent with previous research indicating that poor maternal nutritional status adversely affects fetal growth and increases the risk of intrauterine growth restriction (Desta et al., 2019). Inadequate maternal nutritional reserves may impair placental development and nutrient transfer to the fetus, resulting in restricted fetal growth. Similar associations have been reported in developing countries where maternal malnutrition remains prevalent.

Maternal smoking was also found to be significantly associated with LBW, with smoking mothers having nearly twice the odds of delivering LBW infants compared to non-smokers. This finding aligns with previous studies that have demonstrated the harmful effects of tobacco exposure during pregnancy (Asmare et al., 2018). Smoking during pregnancy reduces uteroplacental blood flow and fetal oxygenation, which may lead to impaired fetal growth and reduced birth weight. The biological plausibility of this association strengthens the validity of the present findings.

Absent antenatal care showed the strongest association with low birth weight in this study. Mothers who had fewer than four antenatal visits had significantly higher odds of delivering LBW infants. Adequate antenatal care provides opportunities for early detection and management of pregnancy-related complications, nutritional counseling, iron and folic acid supplementation, and health education. Lack of regular antenatal visits may delay identification of maternal conditions such as anemia or hypertension, thereby increasing the risk of adverse pregnancy outcomes. Similar findings were reported by Asmare et al. (2018), who observed higher proportions of inadequate antenatal care among mothers delivering LBW babies.

Short inter-pregnancy interval was also significantly associated with LBW. Mothers with an interval of less than 18 months between pregnancies had nearly four times higher odds of delivering low birth weight infants. This finding is supported by previous research suggesting that insufficient birth spacing may prevent adequate maternal nutritional and physiological recovery between pregnancies (Momeni et al., 2017). Maternal depletion syndrome may contribute to compromised fetal growth in closely spaced pregnancies.

The findings of this study are consistent with global evidence demonstrating that modifiable maternal factors play a critical role in determining birth weight (WHO & UNICEF, 2004; UNICEF, 2019). The identification of these factors in a tertiary care hospital setting highlights the need for strengthening antenatal services, promoting maternal nutrition, encouraging smoking cessation, and advocating appropriate birth spacing.

Strengths and Limitations

The strengths of this study include its case-control design, adequate sample size, and use of clearly defined operational criteria. However, certain limitations should be acknowledged. As a hospital-based study, the findings may not be generalizable to the wider community. Additionally, reliance on maternal history for some variables may introduce recall bias.

Conclusion

The present hospital-based case-control study demonstrated a significant association between maternal risk factors and low birth weight at a tertiary care hospital. Maternal under nutrition, maternal smoking, absent antenatal care, and short inter-pregnancy interval were all found to be significantly associated with low birth weight. Among these, absent antenatal care showed the strongest association.

These findings highlight that low birth weight is strongly influenced by modifiable maternal factors. Early identification and management of at-risk mothers during pregnancy may substantially

reduce the burden of low birth weight and its associated neonatal complications.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Strengthening Antenatal Care Services:** Pregnant women should be encouraged to attend at least four antenatal visits to ensure early detection and management of pregnancy-related complications.
2. **Nutritional Counseling and Supplementation:** Routine screening for maternal under nutrition should be performed at booking visits. Nutritional support programs should be reinforced, especially for underweight mothers.
3. **Smoking Cessation Programs:** Health education regarding the adverse effects of smoking during pregnancy should be integrated into antenatal care services.
4. **Promotion of Adequate Birth Spacing:** Counseling on family planning and maintaining an inter-pregnancy interval of at least 18 months should be emphasized to reduce adverse birth outcomes.
5. **Further Research:** Community-based studies are recommended to explore additional socioeconomic and environmental determinants of low birth weight.

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